

Elucidation of the higher coking resistance of small versus large nickel nanoparticles in methane dry reforming via computational modeling

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Abstract

Dry reforming of methane (DRM) is a promising utilization process of greenhouse gases, namely CO₂ and CH₄. Nickel-based catalysts are the most popular ones for DRM, because they are inexpensive and relatively active but deactivate rapidly mainly due to carbon formation. Carbon gasification by either partial or complete oxidation is considered to be the main route for carbon free catalysis. To clarify the competition between carbon deposition and carbon gasification in this computational study we modeled formation of C-C and C-O bonds on large and small Ni-nanoparticles (~1 nm). We found that C prefers to penetrate in the subsurface, whereas O prefers to adsorb on the surface of both large and small nickel particles. Formation of CO at low concentration is significantly more exothermic than C₂ formation but the C₂ moiety is formed faster than CO. At low carbon concentration, the formation of C-C bond is not favorable with respect to two C species located in the subsurface region. However, at high C concentrations on the large metal particle multicarbon C_n species are formed; those species are potential precursors for carbon deposits as graphene or coke. On the other hand, the flexibility of the small nickel nanoparticle allows separate monoatomic C to remain stable as subsurface species. Thus, C_n species, considered to be precursors of carbon deposits leading to catalyst deactivation, are found to preferably form on large rather than on small Ni nanoparticles.

1 Introduction

During the past few decades, there has been an increasing global concern over the rise of greenhouse gases. CO₂ and CH₄ are considered to be major contributors that lead to the increase of global warming.¹⁻³ Consequently, their utilization has attracted considerable attention with dry reforming of methane (DRM) (CO₂+CH₄↔2CO+2H₂) being a promising approach to carbon capture and utilization. The process yields syngas (CO + H₂), a versatile intermediate for the chemical industry, for instance for ammonia (Haber-Bosh) and hydrocarbons (Fischer-Tropsch) production. A variety of catalyst classes have exhibited promising catalytic results for DRM.⁴⁻⁶ Noble metals have found to deliver superior activity and stability amongst others⁷⁻¹¹ but their high price and scarcity make them unattractive for the industry. On the contrary, Ni-based catalysts are active and inexpensive but they face deactivation mainly due to sintering and coke deposition on the catalyst.^{12 - 14} Carbon deposits are derived mainly from CH₄ cracking (CH₄↔C+2H₂) and disproportion of CO (Boudouard reaction) (2CO↔CO₂+C).¹⁵ Sintering of the metal particles is also found to have a significant impact on carbon deposition in a number of studies both experimental¹⁶⁻¹⁸ and computational,¹⁸⁻²⁰ suggesting that a decrease of the Ni nanoparticle (NP) size increases activity and minimizes carbon formation. More specifically, Ni nanoparticle size of less than 5 nm could lead to coke-resistant catalysts.²⁰

For the important processes of DRM and coke formation two elementary reaction steps are crucial: monoatomic C species can react with O or another C species on Ni particles to form either CO (R1) or C₂ (R2) species, respectively:

The latter species can be considered as a precursor for graphene and coke formation, which deactivate Ni catalysts. Deeper understanding of these reaction steps could lead to enhanced carbon gasification and potentially coke-free catalysts. In this computational study we clarified the most stable positions of monoatomic C and O, as well as of CO and C₂ species on/in surface/subsurface regions of periodic Ni(111) slab and Ni₇₉ nanoparticle models representing, respectively, large nickel particles and nickel nanoparticles of ~1 nm size. The processes of C and O penetration/emerging to/from the subsurface region from/to the surface, as well as C₂ and CO formation were also considered. So far, more efforts were directed to their formation on the Ni(111) surface.²¹⁻²³ In our study we also considered the possibility for their formation in the subsurface region and investigated a nanostructured catalyst model. The influence of the C concentration on

the modeled processes and formation of longer carbon chains as coke and graphene precursors was also considered.

2 Method and Models

2.1 Computational details

The calculations were carried out with the plane-wave based Vienna ab initio simulation package (VASP)^{24,25} using the generalized-gradient approximation (GGA) in the form of the exchange-correlation functional PW91.²⁶ The interaction between atomic cores and electrons was described by the projector augmented wave (PAW) method.^{27,28} For integration over the Brillouin zone, we used the k point sampling scheme of Monkhorst and Pack²⁹ and we invoked Methfessel-Paxton technique³⁰ with width of 0.1 eV to accelerate convergence; the final total energies were extrapolated to zero smearing. We adopted an energy cutoff of 415 eV. All calculations are spin-polarized. The average magnetization of Ni atoms in the pristine Ni₇₉ and Ni(111) models is similar, 0.73±0.02 and 0.66±0.02, respectively.

Transition state (TS) structures are obtained by applying the dimer³¹ or the climbing-image nudged elastic band (CI-NEB)^{32,33} methods. In the latter case we used eight images of the system to form a discrete approximation of the path between fixed end-points. The TS structures obtained in this way were refined until the forces on atomic centers were all below 2×10⁻⁴ eV pm⁻¹.

The reported binding energies E_b of the adsorbed/absorbed C and O species were calculated as $E_b = -(E_{ad} + E_{sub} - E_{ad/sub})$; there, E_{ad} is the total (spin-polarized ground-state) energy of the C atomic adsorbate or 1/2 O₂ molecule in the gas phase, E_{sub} is the total energy of the Ni substrate (either or not containing pre-ad(ab)sorbed species) and $E_{ad/sub}$ is the total energy of the substrate with all the adsorbates in the optimized geometry. With this definition, negative E_b values indicate a favorable interaction, i.e. energy release during the process under scrutiny.

2.2 Ni(111) slab model

The employed model is an ideal Ni(111) single crystal surface. The surface was modeled as six-layer slab, repeated in a supercell geometry with a vacuum spacing of at least 1 nm between the neighboring slabs. The adsorbates were bound to one side of the slab models, and were allowed to relax during geometry optimizations together with the three adjacent (“upper”) layers of the substrate. The three “bottom” layers of the slabs were kept fixed at the theoretical bulk-terminated geometry, where Ni-Ni distances are 248 pm. The unit cell is (3×3), which corresponds to coverage of 1/9 when one species is adsorbed on the surface. All the calculations were carried out using a

5×5×1 k-point grid.

2.3 Ni₇₉ Nanoparticle

We employed a truncated octahedral Ni₇₉ NP model exhibiting (111) facets consisting of twelve Ni atoms together with very small (100) facets from only four Ni atoms.³⁴ Ni₇₉ has been positioned in a cubic cell with the lattice parameter $a = 2.0$ nm, which ensures vacuum spacing ~1 nm between all atoms in the neighboring cells. Calculations of the discrete particles are performed at the Γ point.

2.4 Sorption positions

Atomic species can be adsorbed or absorbed on several positions of Ni(111) slab and Ni₇₉ NP models (Fig. 1). The notation of different positions was based on analogous notation for palladium models, reported earlier.³⁵ The three-fold hollow Ni₃ adsorption sites can be of *hcp* (hexagonal close packed) or *fcc* (face-centered cubic) type, depending if their centre is above a Ni atom or hollow position from the subsurface layer, respectively. The corresponding tetrahedral and octahedral sites beneath them, between the surface and subsurface Ni layers, are denoted as *tss* and *oss*. For Ni(111) slab only the *hcp/tss* and *fcc/oss* combinations of surface/subsurface sites exist. On Ni₇₉ NP there are more types of surface/subsurface sites located at facets, edges or corners: at the center (*cen*) of a (111) facet, at the edge between two (111) facets (*edg*), or near the corner between one (111) and one (100) facets (*cor*), see Figure 1. The *tss* site below a surface Ni atom is denoted as *tss'*.

In the models with low adsorbate coverage, one atom on the surface/facet, the surface coverage in the two cases is similar: 1/9 and 1/12 for the slab model and for the Ni₇₉ nanoparticle, respectively. At the highest carbon coverage the values are 1 in case of slab model and 7/12 in case of the nanoparticle.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Sorption of C and O on/in Ni(111) and Ni₇₉

Our calculations show that when atomic C interacts with Ni(111) slab model it prefers to stay in the subsurface region in *oss* position than to be adsorbed on the surface in accordance with previous theoretical results.^{21,22,36-38} The binding energy of C in *oss* subsurface position is calculated to be -722 kJ/mol (Table 1), this result also collaborates with previous studies where the corresponding value is above -700 kJ/mol.^{22,36-38} This position is more stable than positions on the surface by more than 50 kJ/mol (Table 1). The other investigated subsurface position, *tss*, is not stable and the C

atom moves to *oss* during the geometry optimization. The most stable surface position on Ni(111) slab model is *hcp*, which is more stable only by 5 kJ/mol than *fcc* position in line with previous results.^{22,36-38}

The same trends are also valid when a C atom interacts with Ni₇₉ (Table 2). Subsurface positions are more stable than positions on the surface by 20–40 kJ/mol. The difference in the stabilities of surface and subsurface sites is smaller than in the case of Ni(111) slab model due to the larger flexibility of the Ni₇₉ NP model compared to the slab model. Interestingly, a surface reconstruction occurs when C species is located at *hcp-edg* position. This leads to large stabilization of the C species at this position and it becomes equally stable as the subsurface positions (Fig. 2). In this structure C interacts with four Ni atoms on the surface at fourfold hollow position, which appeared as a result of the reconstruction. Reconstruction also occurs when C is located at *tss-cor* subsurface position (Fig. 2). Here, C atom moves to the surface plane of Ni atoms. Hence, the stability of such C atom is close to the stability of the other surface positions.

We also considered the process of penetration of C atom from surface *fcc* and *fcc-cen* positions to subsurface positions below, *oss* and *oss-cen*, respectively on Ni(111) and Ni₇₉ models. The barriers in both cases are similar about 80 kJ/mol, while the process is more exothermic on the slab model than in the case of Ni₇₉ nanoparticles (Table 2). A similar barrier of 79 kJ/mol for C penetration from *fcc* to *oss* positions in the case of Ni(111) slab model was also calculated by Janthon et al.³⁶ using the same PW91 functional.

The most stable positions for O interacting with the Ni(111) slab models are *fcc* and *hcp*, the E_b values with respect to a half O₂ molecule are -236 and -225 kJ/mol, respectively (Table 1). Subsurface positions are less stable than adsorption positions on the Ni(111) surface by more than 220 kJ/mol. The most stable position of O interacting with Ni₇₉ NP is again on the surface of (111) facet of the NP at *fcc-edg* position, -249 kJ/mol (Table 2). The other two surface positions, *fcc-cen* and *hcp-cor*, have very similar stability, -242 kJ/mol, while the *hcp-edg* position is less stable than them by 20 kJ/mol. All subsurface positions are unstable and O species in these positions emerge on the surface during geometry optimization. In one of the cases O moves to a bridge position at the edge between two (111) facets, which is expected to be one of the most stable bridge positions of the NP, since both Ni centers are low coordinated; in this case E_b is -223 kJ/mol (Table 2).

The barrier for the process of penetration of an O atom from surface *fcc* positions to subsurface positions below *oss* on Ni(111) is as high as 237 kJ/mol, while the process is endothermic by essentially the same amount of energy, 233 kJ/mol (Table 3). Hence, the backward process of emerging of subsurface O on the Ni(111) surface possesses a marginal barrier of only 4 kJ/mol and is highly exothermic. In the case of Ni₇₉ NP, we were even unable to find a local

minimum for O in the *oss-cen* position, since the O species emerges on the surface during the geometry optimization.

3.2 Sorption of C₂ and CO on/in bare Ni(111) and Ni₇₉ models

We modeled several locations of the C₂ and CO species at the surface and subsurface regions. When the C₂ species is located on the surface of the Ni(111) each of the C atoms interacts with three Ni atoms at three-fold hollow positions (Fig. 3). We modeled also two structures where C₂ is located in the subsurface region, C_{2-*oss-tss*'}/Ni(111) and C_{2-*oss-tss*}/Ni(111), the extensions indicate the initial positions of C atoms. In the structure C_{2-*oss-tss*'}/Ni(111) the C-C bond was broken during the geometry optimization and both monoatomic C species are located in *oss* positions in the optimized structure. This structure is more stable by 45 kJ/mol than the C₂/Ni(111) structure (Table 4), where C₂ is adsorbed on the surface. Hence, one can conclude that at low concentrations C will prefer to occupy subsurface positions as monoatomic species than to segregate on the surface. In the structure C_{2-*oss-tss*}/Ni(111) a reconstruction of the surface occurs. In the optimized structure the C₂ moiety moves close to the surface level, while one of the Ni atoms is pushed above the surface. This structure is less stable than the C₂/Ni(111) structure by 53 kJ/mol (Table 4).

The coordination mode of the C₂ moiety on the surface (111) facet of Ni₇₉ is the same as in the C₂/Ni(111) structure. We modeled two such structures where: (i) C atoms are located at *fcc-cen* and *hcp-edg* positions, C₂/Ni₇₉, and (ii) C atoms are located at *fcc-cor* and *hcp-edg* positions C_{2-*a*}/Ni₇₉. In the latter structure both C atoms are located at low coordinated edge and corner atoms, but it is more stable by only 3 kJ/mol than the C₂/Ni₇₉ structure where one of the C atoms is located at terrace *fcc-cen* site, which has higher coordination saturation than edge and corner sites (Table 4).

We also tried two structures where C₂ is located in the subsurface region, C_{2-*oss-tss*'}/Ni₇₉ and C_{2-*oss-tss*}/Ni₇₉. In both cases we found two local minima. In the more stable structures, C_{2-*oss-tss*'}/Ni₇₉ and C_{2-*oss-tss*}/Ni₇₉, during the geometry optimizations the C-C bond was broken and the C species initially located at *tss* and *tss'* positions emerged on the surface. This process is facilitated by the large flexibility of the NP which leads to four-fold coordination of the C atoms on the surface (Fig. 3). Those two structures are equally stable as the C₂/Ni₇₉ structure (Table 4). In the other two found minima C_{2-*oss-tss*'-a}/Ni₇₉ and C_{2-*oss-tss*-a}/Ni₇₉, the C₂ species stay intact after geometry optimization and a reconstruction of the metal surface occurs similar to the C_{2-*oss-tss*}/Ni(111) structure. Again, in the optimized structures the C₂ moiety moves at the surface level, while one of the Ni atoms is pushed above the surface. However, these two structures C_{2-*oss-tss*'-a}/Ni₇₉ and C_{2-*oss-tss*-a}/Ni₇₉ are less stable by 56 and 67 kJ/mol, respectively, than the corresponding structures where the C-C bond was broken, C_{2-*oss-tss*'}/Ni₇₉ and C_{2-*oss-tss*}/Ni₇₉.

We also modeled a structure where both C atoms of the C₂ species are located in the *oss-cen* position, C_{2-cen-cen}/Ni₇₉, however, during the geometry optimization the C-C bond was broken and one of the C species emerged on the surface. In the final structure C species are located at *fcc-cen* and *oss-cen* positions. This structure is less stable by 86 kJ/mol than the structure C₂/Ni₇₉ structure (Table 3).

Two structures with two separate subsurface C atoms were also considered, as reference structures C_{2-oss-cen-edg}/Ni₇₉ and C_{2-oss-edg-edg}/Ni₇₉. In the first structure C atoms are located at *oss-cen* and *oss-edg* positions, while in the second one C atoms are located at two *oss-edg* sites of one (111) facet. Both structures are more stable than C₂ species located on the surface by more than 25 kJ/mol.

Additionally, we modeled the interaction of a CO moiety with Ni₇₉ and Ni(111) models at various surface and subsurface positions. When we put CO on the surface at the same coordination mode as C₂ species during the geometry optimization, the O atom detaches from the surface and the CO molecule remains perpendicularly bound to the surface via the C atom, which interacts with Ni surface at three fold coordination. We modeled also two structures where CO is located in the subsurface region, CO-*oss-tss'*/Ni(111) and CO-*oss-tss*/Ni(111) (Fig. 4). In both cases, during the geometry optimization the C-O bond was broken and O moves from subsurface *tss'* and *tss* positions to three fold hollow positions on the surface, while the C species stayed at *oss* position. Both structures are less stable by more than 80 kJ/mol than the structure CO/Ni(111) (Fig. 4) with intact CO molecule (Table 4).

We modeled two structures where CO is adsorbed on the (111) facet of Ni₇₉ NP (Fig. 4). The structure where CO is adsorbed close to the edge of the NP, CO-*a*/Ni₇₉, is more stable by 9 kJ/mol than the structure where CO is adsorbed at the center of the facet, CO/Ni₇₉ (Table 4).

3.3 Sorption of C on/in Ni(111) and Ni₇₉ models at high carbon coverage

In order to simulate a Ni system at high C concentration, we considered a Ni(111) model at a coverage of 1 ML, i.e. we saturated by nine C atoms all most favorable subsurface *oss* positions of our 3×3 slab model. We found two minima for this system. In the first one, C₉/Ni(111), all the C species remain monoatomic with binding energy per C atom of -609 kJ/mol (Fig. 5, Table 5). It is by 113 kJ/mol lower as an absolute value than the low coverage case where only one C atom is adsorbed in octahedral subsurface position of Ni(111) model, -722 kJ/mol (Table 1). In the other located minimum, C_{9-a}/Ni(111) (Fig. 5), the C atoms form chains and the Ni surface layer is strongly perturbed. This structure is significantly more stable, by 478 kJ/mol (e.g. by 53 kJ/mol per C atom), than the first one, C₉/Ni(111) (Table 5). The binding energy per C atom is -662 kJ/mol,

which is lower as an absolute value by 60 kJ/mol than the corresponding value of a single C species located at the *oss* position, implying that such subsurface C_n species can be formed only at high C concentration. Thus, at high carbon coverage on Ni(111), the formation of carbon chains is favorable. These C_n species can be considered as precursors of graphene and coke formation, moreover the C atoms in the longest C_5 chain formed during our calculations have characteristics of C atoms in sp^2 hybridization: the C-C-C angles are $\sim 120^\circ$, while the C-C distances 143-149 pm are only slightly longer than those in aromatic systems.

A structure with seven subsurface C^{oss} species in the Ni_{79} NP was also modeled, C_7/Ni_{79} (Fig. 5). Due to significantly higher flexibility of the NP, C species are stabilized as monoatomic subsurface species. This larger flexibility can be seen by the increase of the diameter of the surface (111) facet by 125 pm (from 722 to 847 pm, including three Ni-Ni distances), when the seven C^{oss} species were introduced in the subsurface region. Surprisingly, the binding energy per C atom is -709 kJ/mol (Table 5), which is the same as the E_b value calculated at low coverage when only one C^{oss} species was introduced in the subsurface region (Table 2). We considered structures with one additional C species (in addition to the seven C^{oss} species) located on the surface or in subsurface region. When this C species is located at the surface *hcp-edg* position, $C^{hcp}C_7/Ni_{79}$ (Fig. 5), its E_b is only -534 kJ/mol (Table 5), which is by 136 kJ/mol lower than the corresponding value, -670 kJ/mol, when the subsurface region is not populated by seven C^{oss} species (Table 2). If the surface C species is located at *fcc-cen* site, $C^{fcc}C_7/Ni_{79}$ (Fig. 5), it forms a C_2 moiety with the C^{oss} species right below. The E_b of the additional C^{fcc} species is -590 kJ/mol (Table 5). The most stable structure found is when C is located in *tss'* position, $C^{tss'}C_7/Ni_{79}$ (Fig. 5), here this C species forms again a C_2 moiety with another C species located at *oss-cen* position. The formed C_2 moiety emerges on the surface during the geometry optimization, which leads to a reconstruction of the metal surface. In this case the E_b of the additional $C^{tss'}$ species is as high as -772 kJ/mol, which is even larger as an absolute value by 63 kJ/mol than the corresponding value for the most stable position of single C species interacting with Ni_{79} , -709 kJ/mol. The C_2 moiety is also formed, when the additional C species is located initially at *tss* position, $C^{tss}C_7/Ni_{79}$ (Fig. 5), in this case the structure is less stable by 147 kJ/mol than the previous one with E_b of the C^{tss} species of -625 kJ/mol (Table 5). Thus, at high carbon coverage on nickel nanoparticle, no carbon chains are formed but carbon species remain isolated in the subsurface region or form C_2 moieties, when subsurface positions are completely occupied.

3.4 Energetics for formation of C₂ and CO species

As we already discussed in the Introduction, at the catalytic conditions of DRM monoatomic C species on Ni particles may undergo two types of elementary reaction steps:

Reaction step (R1) as part of the DRM process is catalytically desired for cleaning the catalyst's surface. Reaction step (R2) leads to formation of C₂* species, which can be considered as a precursor for graphene and coke formation, which drastically reduces the catalytic activity of Ni, hence, this reaction step is undesired in DRM.

We considered both reaction steps at Ni₇₉ and Ni(111) models: pristine and containing subsurface C species (Fig. S1 in ESI, Table 6). On the pristine Ni(111) surface both reaction steps are strongly exothermic and R1 is more exothermic by 70 kJ/mol than R2. When both reaction steps occur on Ni₇₉ NP the exothermicity decreases by 15-20 kJ/mol since in the initial state structure one of the monoatomic species is located close to the edge of the NP. As shown above, adsorption sites of the individual atoms at the edge are more favorable than the ones at the center of the NP facet. Despite of larger exothermicity of R1 with respect to R2, the barriers for R1 calculated on Ni(111) and Ni₇₉ NP models, 124 and 147 kJ/mol, respectively, are about twice larger than the barriers for R2 calculated on the same models, 64 and 64 kJ/mol, respectively, manifesting the easy coke formation on the Ni surface.³⁹ Similar theoretical results were obtained by Basaran et al.⁴⁰ for R2 on Ni(111), where the barrier and reaction energy were calculated to be 71 and -71 kJ/mol, respectively.

We also investigated the influence of the concentration of subsurface C on both reaction energies. When three subsurface C species are introduced, R1 becomes more exothermic by 24 kJ/mol in the case of the Ni(111) slab model and more endothermic by ~25 kJ/mol when the reaction occurs on the NP model, while the reaction energy of R2 does not change in either case (Table 6). Covering the subsurface region of the NP by seven C^{oss} species significantly change both reaction energies: R1 becomes slightly endothermic by 12 kJ/mol, on the contrary R2 is exothermic by 254 kJ/mol. This result implies that at high C concentrations the formation of C-C bonds will be facilitated due to the presence of subsurface carbon species, while the C-O formation will be suppressed.

4 Summary and Conclusions

Our theoretical results show that a monoatomic C species is more stable in the subsurface area than on the surface when it interacts with nickel nanoparticle and Ni(111) slab surface as models of small and large metal particles, respectively. A similar behavior of C species was found when it interacts with Pd particles.^{35,36,41} Monoatomic O species prefers to stay on the surface, rather than to penetrate in the subsurface area when interacting with Ni(111) slab and Ni₇₉ nanoparticle models. At low carbon coverage the intact C₂ species, if formed, is more stable when it is located on the Ni surface than in the subsurface region. However, under those conditions C atoms prefers to stay as monoatomic C subsurface species in octahedral positions rather than to form C₂ species on the Ni(111) surface. At high subsurface C concentration, our results suggest that in the large Ni particles C_n species (potential precursors for formation of carbon deposits as coke or graphene) are formed, which causes large reconstructions on the Ni surface. On the contrary, monoatomic C species exist on small Ni nanoparticles due to their larger flexibility. This important property is likely the reason for the higher coke resistance of the Ni nanoparticles in line with the experimental results.²⁰

The most stable state of the CO moiety is the formation of a CO molecule coordinated linearly via the C atom in three-fold position on the Ni(111) surface on both large particle and nanoparticle models. All the attempts to optimize the CO molecule in the subsurface region failed, since the C-O bond broke during the geometry optimization and O species emerged on the surface, while C stayed in the subsurface region.

At low concentrations formation of a C₂ moiety on both Ni(111) slab and Ni₇₉ nanoparticle models is exothermic if both monoatomic C species are already on the surface, but endothermic when C species are at the most stable subsurface octahedral sites. On the other hand, formation of CO at low concentration is significantly more exothermic than C₂ formation, even when we start with the most stable positions for the monoatomic C and O species, *oss* and *fcc*, respectively. If we consider the kinetics of the process, the C₂ moiety is formed faster than CO at low concentrations.

The increase of the subsurface C concentration facilitates energetically the C-C bond formation, while C-O formation is hindered and it even becomes slightly endothermic. These results suggested that in order to facilitate C-O formation one needs to reduce the concentration of C on the catalyst as much as possible. In order to diminish the effect of the kinetic preference for formation of a C-C bond and to benefit from the thermodynamic preference towards C-O bond formation, the process should be performed at higher temperature. In this case the entropy may also contribute to the process facilitating the CO desorption. On the other hand, if the desired process is graphene

formation, then the reaction should be performed at lower temperature and on large nickel particles, exposing extended Ni(111) surfaces.

We would like also to recall one limitation of our study that interaction of the adsorbates is considered only on the (111) surface, while other surfaces such as (100) and (110) can be also catalytically important though their concentrations are significantly lower than the concentration of (111) surface.

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Table 1

Binding energies, E_b (in kJ/mol), of C and O (with respect to $1/2$ O_2 molecule) at various surface and subsurface positions of Ni(111) slab model.

position	$E_b(C)$	$E_b(1/2O_2)$
<i>fcc</i>	-665	-236
<i>hcp</i>	-670	-225
<i>oss</i>	-722	-3
<i>tss</i>	- ^a	- ^a

^a C and O move to *oss* position during the geometry optimization

Table 2

Binding energies, E_b (in kJ/mol), of C and O (with respect to $1/2$ O_2 molecule) at various surface and subsurface positions of Ni_{79} nanoparticle.

	$E_b(C)$	$E_b(1/2O_2)$
<i>fcc-cen</i>	-676	-242
<i>fcc-edg</i>	-669	-249
<i>hcp-cor</i>	-673	-242
<i>hcp-edg</i>	-702 ^a	-221
<i>oss-cen</i>	-696	- ^c
<i>oss-edg</i>	-709	- ^d
<i>tss-cor</i>	-671 ^b	- ^e
<i>tss-edg</i>	-702	- ^e

^a surface reconstruction occurred and C interacts with four surface Ni atoms; ^b surface reconstruction occurred and C moves on the level of surface Ni atoms; ^c O atom moves on the surface at *fcc* position during geometry optimization ^d O atom moves to bridge position, E_b is -223 kJ/mol; ^e O atom moves on the surface at *hcp* position during geometry optimization

Table 3

Reaction barriers and reaction energies, ΔE , for penetration of C and O from surface to the subsurface regions of Ni(111) slab and Ni₇₉ nanoparticle models. All values are in kJ/mol.

	barrier	ΔE
C/Ni ₇₉ : <i>fcc-cen</i> \rightarrow <i>oss-cen</i>	79	-20
C/Ni(111) <i>fcc</i> \rightarrow <i>oss</i>	81	-57
O/Ni ₇₉ : <i>fcc-cen</i> \rightarrow <i>oss-cen</i>	- ^a	- ^a
O/Ni(111) <i>fcc</i> \rightarrow <i>oss</i>	237	233

^a O in *oss-cen* position emerges on the surface during the geometry optimization

Table 4

Relative energies, E_{rel} , (in kJ/mol) of C_2 and CO located at various surface and subsurface positions on/in Ni(111) slab and Ni_{79} NP models.

Structure	E_{rel}
$\text{C}_2/\text{Ni}(111)$	0
$\text{C}_2\text{-oss-tss}'/\text{Ni}(111)$	-45 ^a
$\text{C}_2\text{-oss-tss}/\text{Ni}(111)$	53 ^b
$\text{C}_2/\text{Ni}_{79}$	0
$\text{C}_2\text{-a}/\text{Ni}_{79}$	-3
$\text{C}_2\text{-cen-cen}/\text{Ni}_{79}$	86 ^d
$\text{C}_2\text{-oss-tss}/\text{Ni}_{79}$	1 ^{c,d}
$\text{C}_2\text{-oss-tss-a}/\text{Ni}_{79}$	68
$\text{C}_2\text{-oss-tss}'/\text{Ni}_{79}$	0 ^{c,d}
$\text{C}_2\text{-oss-tss}'\text{-a}/\text{Ni}_{79}$	56
$\text{C}_2\text{-oss-cen-edg}/\text{Ni}_{79}$	-27
$\text{C}_2\text{-oss-edg-edg}/\text{Ni}_{79}$	-26
$\text{CO}/\text{Ni}(111)$	0
$\text{CO-oss-tss}/\text{Ni}(111)$	105 ^e
$\text{CO-oss-tss}'/\text{Ni}(111)$	81 ^e
$\text{CO-a}/\text{Ni}_{79}$	0
CO/Ni_{79}	9

^a C-C bond was broken during the geometry optimization and both C species occupy *oss* positions;

^b reconstruction occurred: one of the Ni atoms moves above the surface, C_2 species moves at the surface level; ^c reconstruction occurred; ^d C-C bond was broken; ^e C-O bond was broken

Table 5

Average binding energies, $E_b(\text{C})^{\text{average}}$ of all C atoms and binding energies, $E_b(\text{C})$, of the additional C atom with respect to the NP system with fully covered subsurface region $\text{C}^{\text{OSS}}_7/\text{Ni}_{79}$. All energies are in kJ/mol.

Structure	$E_b(\text{C})^{\text{average}}$	$E_b(\text{C})^a$
$\text{C}_9/\text{Ni}(111)$	-609	
$\text{C}_9\text{-a}/\text{Ni}(111)$	-662	
$\text{C}_7/\text{Ni}_{79}$	-709	
$\text{C}^{\text{fcc}}\text{C}_7/\text{Ni}_{79}$	-694	-590
$\text{C}^{\text{hcp}}\text{C}_7/\text{Ni}_{79}$	-687	-534
$\text{C}^{\text{tss}}\text{C}_7/\text{Ni}_{79}$	-698	-625
$\text{C}^{\text{tss}'}\text{C}_7/\text{Ni}_{79}$	-717	-772

^a E_b of the additional C atom interacting with the $\text{C}_7/\text{Ni}_{79}$ system

Table 6

Reaction energies and barriers (in parenthesis) for the reaction steps: $C^* + O^* \rightarrow CO^*$ (R1) and $C^* + C^* \rightarrow C_2^*$ (R2) occurring at Ni(111) and Ni₇₉ models: bare or containing C species in the subsurface region. All values are in kJ/mol.

	$C^* + O^* \rightarrow CO^*$ (R1)	$C^* + C^* \rightarrow C_2^*$ (R2)
Ni(111)-bare	-154 (124)	-84 (64)
Ni ₇₉ -bare	-134; -137 (147)	-68 (64)
C ₃ /Ni(111)	-178	-85
C ₃ /Ni ₇₉	-110	-67
C ₇ /Ni ₇₉	12	-254

Figure 1. Top view of the surface (dark blue) and subsurface (light blue) atoms at a (111) facet of Ni_{79} NP. Threefold hollow adsorption positions are indicated as: 1) *fcc* in the center region of the facet (*fcc-cen*); 2) *fcc* at the edge of the facet, including one corner Ni atom (*fcc-cor*); 3) *hcp* with one edge Ni atom (*hcp-edg*); 4) *hcp* at the corner between the (111) and (100) facets (*hcp-cor*); The corresponding subsurface octahedral (*oss*, below *fcc*) and tetrahedral (*tss*, below *hcp*) positions are 1) *oss-cen*, 2) *oss-cor*, 3) *tss-edg*, 4) *tss-cor*, 5) tetrahedral subsurface position below the surface Ni atom of the (111) facet (*tss'*).³⁵ Only top two layers are shown for visual clarity.

Figure 2. Surface reconstruction occurred during the geometry optimization when C species are located at *hcp-edge* (top view) and *tss-cor* (side view). Color coding: surface Ni atoms – dark blue, subsurface Ni atoms – light blue, other Ni atoms – white, C – gray.

Figure 3. Optimized structures (side or top views) of C_2 or $C+C$ interacting with surface or subsurface regions of $Ni(111)$ and Ni_{79} models. Color coding: surface Ni atoms – dark blue, subsurface Ni atoms – light blue, other Ni atoms – white, C – gray, O – red; the borders of the unit cell of $Ni(111)$ models are shown with yellow lines.

Figure 4. Optimized structures (side views) of CO interacting with surface or subsurface regions of Ni(111) and Ni₇₉ models. Color coding: surface Ni atoms – dark blue, subsurface Ni atoms – light blue, other Ni atoms – white, C – gray, O – red; the borders of the unit cell of Ni(111) models are shown with yellow lines.

Figure 5. Optimized structures (side or/and top views) of Ni(111) slab and Ni₇₉ NP models at high C subsurface concentrations. Color coding: surface Ni atoms – dark blue, subsurface Ni atoms – light blue, other Ni atoms – white, C – gray; the borders of the unit cell of Ni(111) models are shown with yellow lines.

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